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A new record of *Xeroporcellio pandazisi* Strouhal, 1954, a Balkan member of the tropical family Scleropactidae Verhoeff, 1938 (Crustacea, Isopoda, Oniscidea)

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SUMMARY. A new record of the little-known species *Xeroporcellio pandazisi* Strouhal, 1954 from Montenegro is presented, which significantly extends the known range of this species to the west of the Balkan Peninsula. The population of this species from the new locality is presented in all relevant details, with figures and a brief description. The planned cascade hydroelectric power plants in the Morača River canyon, where this species is present, will certainly threaten the survival of this population.

KEY WORDS: Balkan Peninsula, Montenegro, Morača River Canyon.

INTRODUCTION

The tropical family Scleropactidae has so far 115 known extant species from 28 genera (Boyko et al. 2024). Two thirds of the known species are from the Neotropics (Campos-Filho et al. 2021). All three fossil Scleropactidae species (in two extinct genera) are also known from the Neotropics (Schmalfuss 1980; Broly et al. 2018). Other species are present in the Oriental region (subfamily Toradjinae), Madagascar (a genus with two species) and Balkan Peninsula (three species). This unusual distribution of the family supports the suspicion that it is not monophyletic (Schmidt 2003, 2007, 2008).

In the Balkan fauna, the family Scleropactidae is known by three species from two genera, *Xeroporcellio* Strouhal, 1954 and *Kithironiscus* Schmalfuss, 1995. The troglobitic genus *Kithironiscus* is present with two species: *Kithironiscus parag-*

amiani Schmalfuss, 1995 from a cave on Greek island Kythira, and *Kithironiscus dobrogicus* Tabacaru & Giurginca, 2003 from a sinkhole and drills in a karst area (next to the famous Movile cave) in the south of Dobrudja in Romania. The genus *Xeroporcellio* with the species *Xeroporcellio pandazisi* Strouhal, 1954 is known from two localities in the Ionian part of Greece (Fig. 1). It shows a clear family affiliation, while this is not so clear with the genus *Kithironiscus*.

In the 70's in the last century, a population of *Xeroporcellio pandazisi* was discov-

Fig. 1. Distribution of *Xeroporcellio pandazisi* (red dots).

ered by Prof. Dr Mladen Karaman in a refuge area in Montenegro near Morača Monastery in Morača River Canyon. It represents a new record of this species, very far from the so far known localities. Strouhal (1954) described the genus and species based on an incomplete specimen and therefore misclassified it into the family Porcellionidae. Prof. M. Karaman recognized the species position in the system of the classification of terrestrial isopods at the time and

was preparing to publish it. Even illustrations were done (not used in this paper). Unfortunately, a long-term serious illness and untimely death prevented him from publishing this interesting finding.

Here I present the species in all relevant details based on specimens from Montenegro, with figures and a short description.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Specimens were collected by sifting leaf litter and soil among rocks and stones of deciduous forest. Specimens were preserved in the field in 70% ethanol and dissected in diluted glycerin. Dissections were done with micro-needles under a dissection

microscope. All separated parts were mounted on slides in glycerin. Photographs were taken using a Zeiss Axio Imager A1 compound microscope equipped with an AxioCam MRc 5 digital camera. Drawings based on photographs were made in Adobe Illustrator CS6 on a Wacom Intuos 2 graphics tablet.

Fig. 2. *Xeroporcellio pandazisi*. A, E ♂, 3.20 mm; B-D ♀, 4.8 mm. **A**, habitus lateral; **B**, cephalothorax, frontal; **C** cephalothorax, lateral; **D**, first antenna; **E**, pleon dorsal. Scale bars: B, C = 1 mm; D = 50 µm; E = 200 µm.

RESULTS

Xeroporcellio pandazisi Strouhal, 1954 (Figs 2-6)

Xeroporcellio pandazisi: Strouhal, 1942, p.148 (mention); 1954, p.588 (figs 38-42); Schmalzfuss, 1979, p.28 (mention)

Kefalloniscus hauseri: Schmalzfuss, 1986, p.282, (figs 1-23)

Xeroporcellio pandazisi: Schmalzfuss, 1995, p.140 (figs 1-7); Schmalzfuss, 2003, p.295 (mention)

MATERIAL EXAMINED. Montenegro, Morača River Canyon, Morača Monastery, 42°45'52.49"N, 19°23'29.80"E: 20-09-1973, leg G. Karaman; ibid. 7♀ 2♂ 5juv. 1-05-1975, leg M. Karaman; ibid. 12♂ 16♀ 30 juv. 1-10-1975, leg M. Karaman; ibid. 18-08-1979, leg M. Karaman; ibid. 1♀, 2juv. 4-05-1997; leg I. Karaman.

DESCRIPTION. Maximum length: ♂, 3.5 mm; ♀, 4.4 mm. Male body as in Fig. 2. The body coloration has faded as a result of preservation, and therefore cannot be described with reliability. Tergites and cephalothorax olive grey. Dorsal surface smooth and shiny. Exoantennal conglobation (Fig. 2A). Cephalothorax (Fig 2B-

Fig. 3. *Xeroporcellio pandazisi*, mandibles, ♀, 4.8 mm. A, right mandible; B, left mandible. Scale bar = 100 µm.

Fig. 4. *Xeroporcellio pandazisi*, mouth parts, ♀, 4.8 mm. **A**, Maxillae 1 exite; **B**, Maxillae 1 endite; **C**, Maxillae 2; **D**, Maxilliped, caudal. Scale bar = 50 μ m.

Fig. 5. *Xeroporcellio pandazisi*. A ♂, 3.50 mm; B-D, ♂, 3.20 mm. A, second antenna; B, pereopod 1, frontal; C, Pereopod 7, caudal; D, uropod, ventral view. Scale bars: A-C = 200 μ m; D = 100 μ m.

C) with frontal shield slightly concave in the middle; transverse groove behind the frontal shield is deepest in its middle part. Lateral lobes short, broadly oval. Eyes composed of 14–16 ommatidia.

First antenna three-jointed (Fig. 2D), with three apical and two subapical aesthetascs; second article shortest. Second antenna with three-jointed flagellum (Fig. 5A). Apical cone is 1.5 times as long as distal flagellar article. Flagellar articles 1 and 2 of the same length.

Right mandible with three-cusped pars incisiva, two-cusped lacinia mobilis, hairy

Fig. 6. *Xeroporcellio pandazisi*, ♂, 3.50 mm. **A**, Pleopod 1 endopodite and genital papilla; **B**, Pleopod 1 exopodite; **C**, Pleopod 2. Scale bar = 200 μ m.

lobe, tuft of hairy setae with a penicil representing pars molaris and a penicil between last two structures (Fig. 3A). Left mandible with five-cusped pars incisiva, two-cusped lacinia mobilis, hairy lobe with two short penicils, tuft of hairy setae representing pars molaris and a penicil between last two structures (Fig. 3B).

Maxilla 1 exite (Fig. 4A) on the distal margin with group of four stout, simple tooth, and a fifth short one with straight tip; mesal group of six tooth setae slender and of different sizes, two of which are apically cleft. Maxilla 1 endite (Fig. 4B) with 6 elongate penicils, mesodistal end with a short spine.

Maxilla 2 (Fig. 4C) apically bilobate; mesal lobe remarkably narrower than the lateral lobe. Both lobes hairy. Mesal lobe with a marginal field of small sensory setae, and a short seta apically. Lateral lobe with a bit longer seta apically.

Maxilliped palp (Fig. 4D) three-jointed, the proximal article bearing one large seta caudally. Second article on mesal margin with proximal tuft of three short setae, distal tuft of numerous short setae on a socket and a single seta beside; one slender seta on lateral margin. Distal article with distal tuft of numerous setae and a single seta on lateral margin. Maxilliped endite rectangular with rounded distal margin, bearing numerous small setae.

Pereiopod 1 (Fig. 5B) with antennal brush composed of scales on the ventral face of carpus and propodus, covering almost half of the propodus length; carpus with strong terminal seta as long as propodus. Dactylus with apically hirsute dactylar seta, curved unguis seta accompanied by a minute basal seta, short inner claw, one more seta on frontal and caudal face each.

Pereiopod 7 (Fig. 5C), carpus with strong terminal seta as long as propodus.

Male pleopod 1 endopodite (Fig. 6A) with broad base gradually narrowing towards the top, ending with a nipple-like tip; exopodite (Fig. 6B) broad with concave lateral margin, inner margin broadly rounded. Male pleopod 2 (Fig. 6C) endopodite with wide basal article; distal one thin and membranous in terminal half; exopodite distally elongated and slightly hairy, with concave lateral and straight mesal margin.

Uropod (Fig. 5D) protopodite subquadrangular; exopodite curved, slightly shorter than endopodite.

REMARKS. In comparison with drawings of *X. pandazisi* in Strouhal (1954) and Schmalzfuss (1986, 1995) there are some differences between Greek and Montenegrin populations. The male pleopod 2 exopodite in Greek populations is out-curved terminally while in the Montenegrin population it is straight. The male pleopod 2 endopodite distal article in Montenegrin population is narrowed near the half of its length, while in Greek populations it is narrowed at the beginning of the apical half of its length.

DISCUSSION

The Balkan Peninsula is faunistically an extremely interesting region on a world scale. In a small space, there are alternating areas with a peculiar fauna, numerous endemics and sometimes completely unexpected elements. The great heterogeneity of the Balkan fauna in terms of its origin is especially expressed. This is because the areas of the Balkan Peninsula were intersections of different biogeographical regions, both in the near and distant geological past. Although it is still early to assess the overall diversity because this area is largely still underexplored, we can say that it is extremely and unusually rich for areas with a temperate climate. It is primarily the result of the dynamic geotectonics of the Mediterranean,

complex orography and the spatial distribution of karst areas, which crucially provide numerous refugial habitats.

Gorges and canyons are the most common refugial habitats in the Balkans, where the elements of the old Tertiary fauna survived the dramatic climatic changes during the Pleistocene. Particularly significant are those that extend in the north-south direction (open to the south) in which the fauna could move north or south without barriers in the direction of the optimal gradient of physical conditions. One of these is the Morača River Canyon in Montenegro. In the south it is under the strong influence of the Mediterranean, while in the north, inserted among high mountains, it is under the strong influence of the continental climate. This extremely attractive and faunistically little-explored canyon is slated to be submerged almost entirely. Serious plans have been underway for more than 40 years and are very close to being realized. Eight cascading hydropower plants are planned to be built, five in the canyon itself and three on the tributaries.

There were plans to submerge the Tara River Canyon, which is slightly further north and opens to the north as part of the Danube basin. Faunistically, it is far less significant compared to the Morača River Canyon. As it is much better known, due to tourist rafting and hiking tours, its undoubted beauty, and as part of the Durmitor National Park, Tara River Canyon has been successfully preserved by coordinated international action. I'm afraid there is no such will in the case of Morača River Canyon.

The locality itself where *X. pandazisi* is present is the type locality of two species, *Ovaliptila willemsei* (Karaman, 1975) (Orthoptera) and *Dicranolasma mladeni* Karaman, 1990 (Opiliones), as well as one currently undescribed species of the genus *Cyphophthalmus* (Opiliones). A population of a very rare endemic species of Opiliones is also present in this locality, in terms of body length the largest harvestmen in the world, *Trogulus torosus* (Simon, 1885). This is one of the few localities where this species is present outside of caves. Otherwise, it is present in a small area of the southern Dinarides (Schönhofer et al. 2013), mainly in caves.

As the laws of economics are as inexorable as the hunger for money of the ruling elites is insatiable, there is no place for the illusion that reason will prevail and the Morača River Canyon will be preserved in its current state. That's why I recommend colleagues to explore it as soon as possible and others to visit it and experience all its unforgettable beauties, on time.

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